

A New Method for Determination of Furfural in Food and Beverage Samples

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A spectrophotometric method for the determination of furfural is described. It is based on the colour reaction of furfural with 4-methoxybenzaldehyde to form a red violet dye with maximum absorbance at 575 nm and obeys Beer's law in the range of 0.08–1 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of furfural. The molar absorptivity of the colour system was $39.3 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. SD and RSD were 0.02 and $\pm 1.02\%$ respectively for $n = 10$. The method is free from many organic and inorganic interferences and has been successfully applied for the trace level determination of furfural in air, alcoholic beverages and food products.

Looking to the significance and toxicity of furfural, several methods such as voltammetry¹, hplc², gc, mass spectrometry³ and a number of colorimetric methods^{4–8} have been reported for its determination. Some of the colorimetric reagents like benzidine, xylydine, phenylenediamine are carcinogens while others are less sensitive for trace analysis of furfural.

In this communication a method is proposed for the determination of furfural by reacting it with 4-methoxybenzaldehyde to form a red-violet dye. The method has been successfully applied for the trace level analysis of furfural in various food and beverage samples.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectrum of the dye formed has maximum absorbance at 575 nm. The reagent blank shows only negligible absorbance at this wavelength. The colour development was complete within 5 min. The stability of the dye was studied by measuring absorbance values of the colour system for 6 h. The dye formed was found stable for 4–5 h in glacial acetic acid as well as in sulphuric acid media.

The method is fairly reproducible and obeys Beer's law in the range 2–25 μg of furfural (0.08–1 ppm) in 25 ml of final solution. Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were found to be $39.6 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.003 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively.

The effect of pH and temperature on colour development was studied. Constant and maximum

absorbance values were obtained in the pH range 1.0–3.6, which was maintained by glacial acetic acid or sulphuric acid. Colour development was immediate in the temperature range 90–100°.

The effect of various diverse ions likely to coexist with 20 μg of furfural was examined by adding varying amounts of diverse ion solutions to it and measuring the deviation in absorbance. The tolerance limit (concentration which may vary the result by $\pm 2\%$) of diverse ions in $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ are as follows : ethanol, 30000; acetic acid, 25000; aniline, benzene, pyridine and cyanide, 10000; n-butanol, 5000; isoamyl alcohol and vaniline, 3000; methanol and phenol, 2000; α -naphthol, 2500; sulphite and sulphate, 1800; biacarbonate, 1600; benzaldehyde, 1200; ammonium, nitrite and nitrate, 1000; formaldehyde, 800 ; Fe^{II}, Fe^{III} and fluoride, 600; Cr^{IV}, 500; Ni^{III} and Cu^{II}, 250. Presence of metal ions Cu^{II}, Ni^{III} and Fe^{III} expedited the colour development under the optimum conditions.

Collection and absorption efficiency for the analysis of furfural in air was determined as reported earlier⁹. About 98–100% absorption was achieved in 0.10% solution of MBH. The optimum flow rate for maximum collection was found in the range 0.250–0.750 $\text{dm}^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$ for a sampling time of 10 min. It was found that 1 ml of 0.5% MBH, 5 ml H₂SO₄ and 2–3 min heating (boiling water) were sufficient for complete colour reaction.

Application : The validity of the method was checked by determining furfural in commercial alcohol, wheat flour and distillery waste. Analytical

values obtained by the proposed method were found to be in agreement with those obtained by aniline-acetic acid method⁵ (Table 1).

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF ANALYSIS IN VARIOUS SAMPLES

Sample	Furfural found ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) ^a	
	Proposed method	Aniline-acetic acid method
Commercial alcohol	18.10	17.95
	16.50	16.50
	17.20	17.15
	17.65	17.75
	22.10	22.00
Whisky	15.75	15.80
	16.40	16.35
	19.60	19.40
Distillery waste	66.10	66.65
	60.05	59.80
	46.10	46.00
Wheat flour ^b	4.05	4.20
	4.10	4.08
	4.60	4.90
	4.50	4.55

^aMean of three replicate analyses.

^bResults are expressed in $\mu\text{g}/5$ g of wheat flour.

Commercial alcohol, distillery waste and whisky sample (50 ml) was distilled and 30 ml of the distillate was collected at the temperature range

TABLE 2—COMPARISON OF PRECISION OF THE METHOD*

Method	<i>n</i>	\bar{x}	SD	SD ² $\times 10^{-6}$	<i>F</i> **
Proposed method	10	1.97	$\left(\frac{0.024}{9}\right)^{1/2}$	256	= 2.383
			= 0.0160		
Aniline-acetic acid method	8	1.94	$\left(\frac{0.0043}{7}\right)^{1/2}$	610	
			= 0.0247		

*Ref. 10; since calculated value of (B^2/A^2) is less than the standard value of 'F' there is no significant difference in precision of two methods; standard value of *F* at 95% confidence level is 3.29; *n* = no. of analyses, \bar{x} = mean, SD = standard deviation.

50–165° and the distillate was analysed by the recommended procedure. Wheat flour sample (5 g) was extracted with benzene (10 + 10 + 5 ml). Benzene was then evaporated off in a boiling water-

bath. The content was rinsed with 50% ethanol (5 ml) and the solution was analysed for furfural as recommended.

Precision and accuracy : The reproducibility of the method was assessed analysing 2 μg of furfural over a period of 7 days. SD and RSD were found to be 0.02 and $\pm 1.02\%$ respectively. The precision of the method was compared with that of aniline-acetic acid method⁵ (Table 2) and no significant difference was found in precision of the two methods. The average of percentage recovery was 99.3 from real samples.

The proposed method was compared with other reported spectrophotometric methods (Table 3) and this method was found more sensitive and rapid than the others.

The proposed method has enough sensitivity for the trace level analysis of furfural and is also free from most of the organic and inorganic interferences. It is suitable for industrial analysis of furfural in food, food products and beverages.

Experimental

Spectrophotometric measurements were made with a Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer. A PIMCO calibrated rotameters and two 35 ml midjet impingers were used for air sampling.

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade or the best quality commercially available. Stock solution (1 mg ml^{-1}) was prepared by dissolving freshly distilled furfural (100 mg) in 50% ethanol (100 ml). Working standard (1 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) was prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution with water. 4-Methoxybenzaldehyde (MBH) reagent (0.5%) was prepared in concentrated H_2SO_4 and stored in an amber coloured bottle; it was stable for ~ 4 days. Absorbing solution was prepared diluting the above reagent in 1 : 5 ratio with concentrated H_2SO_4 .

Procedure :

In solution : To an aliquot of the sample containing 2–25 μg of furfural was added concentrated H_2SO_4 (2 ml) and MBH (1 ml) were added and the tube was placed in a boiling water-bath for 2 min. The solution was then diluted to 25 ml with glacial acetic acid and its absorbance was measured against a reagent blank at 575 nm.

In air : Air samples containing furfural were drawn through two impingers, each containing 5 ml

TABLE 3—COMPARISON WITH OTHER SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHODS

Method	λ_{\max} nm	Time (min)/ (Temp. °C)	Determination range ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	Remarks
Aniline-acetic acid method ^d	272	5–10 (Room temp.)	1–54	Phenols, and higher alcohols interfere with trace level analyses
Thiosemicarbazide ^b	316	15–20 boiling (100°)	5–50	Aliphatic aldehydes strongly interfere. Can not be applied for low level analysis
Xylidine ^c	500–518	10–15	0.5–4.5	Interferences of aliphatic as well as aromatic aldehydes, phenols, etc.
Benzidine ^c	518	25–30	2–5	The reagent is carcinogenic
Phenylenediamine ^d			1–10	
Present method	575	2–5 (100°)	0.08–1	Free from interferences more sensitive for trace level analysis

^aRef. 5. ^bRef. 8 ^cRef. 6. ^dRef. 4

of the absorbing solution, at a flow rate of 0.250 dm³ min⁻¹ for 10 min. The solution was then placed on a boiling water-bath for 2 min, diluted to 25 ml and its absorbance was measured at 575 nm. Results were evaluated from a calibration curve similarly prepared from standard furfural solution.

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